

1 **Genomic stability shapes metabolic fitness.**

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7 We hypothesized that the overall state of genomic stability in the cell shaped, in most cellular contexts,
8 metabolic fitness. To provide evidence supporting this assertion, we measured total transcription in human
9 breast cancer cells with genetic depletion of the *Blm* helicase possessing functions in maintenance of
10 genome stability. Loss of *Blm* in human cells resulted in activation of the suppressor of glucose,
11 autophagy associated *SOGA1*. A primary molecular consequence of *Blm* silencing was activation of
12 *PFKFB4* together with aldolase, fructose-bisphosphate C (*ALDOC*) activation. Expression of the
13 fructose-bisphosphatase 1 *FBP1* was lost in *Blm*-depleted cells. Silencing of *Blm* resulted in loss of *IDH2*
14 expression. Genomic stability shapes metabolic fitness.

15 Citations

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